

Synthesis, characterization, and molecular and crystalline architectures of two mononuclear mercury(II) iodide complexes containing two tridentate Schiff bases as end-capping ligands

Subhasish Kundu, Kishalay Bhar, Smita Satapathi, Somnath Choubey, Rajarshi Ghosh and Barindra Kumar Ghosh*

Department of Chemistry, The University of Burdwan, Burdwan-713 104, West Bengal, India

E-mail : barin_1@yahoo.co.uk Fax : 91-342-2530452

Manuscript received online 29 June 2012, accepted 18 July 2012

Abstract : Two neutral mononuclear mercury(II) iodide compounds [Hg(L1)I₂] (1) and [Hg(L2)I₂] (2) [L1 = (*N,N*-diethyl-*N'*-(pyridin-2-yl)formylidene)ethane-1,2-diamine, and L2 = (*N,N*-diethyl-*N'*-(pyridin-2-yl)benzylidene)ethane-1,2-diamine] have been synthesized and characterized. X-Ray structural analyses show that in 1/2, metal(II) center has a distorted square pyramidal geometry with an HgN₃I₂ chromophore. Two individual mononuclear units of 1 are interlocked through weak $\pi\cdots\pi$ interactions resulting in a discrete dimer; the supramolecular dimeric entities are oriented in such a fashion that vitiates further $\pi\cdots\pi$ interaction among them. In 2, the monomeric units are self-assembled through C-H \cdots I interactions into a 1D chain along *a*-axis. 1 and 2 show thermal stability up to 160 and 290 °C, respectively, and display intraligand ¹(π - π^*) fluorescence in DMF solutions at room temperature.

Keywords : Mononuclear mercury(II), Schiff base, terminal iodide, X-ray structure, fluorescence.

Introduction

Research on the design and synthesis^{1,2} of well defined mono-, di- and polynuclear mercury(II)³⁻⁶ coordination compounds with a wide range of symmetries and coordination numbers continues unabated in synthetic inorganic chemistry. The mercury(II) compounds show interesting properties in terms of their applications in paper industry and as paints, cosmetics, preservatives, cleaning solutions, manometers, thermostat probes, thermoelectric devices, fluorescent lamps, sensors and mercury batteries⁷⁻¹¹. In this regard, Schiff bases¹² can act as useful blockers due to their ease of preparation, structural varieties and varied denticities and subtle steric and/or electronic effects. Halides^{13,14} are also suitable terminal/bridging units which in combination with Schiff bases and mercury(II) may result in different molecular architectures through their versatile ligational modes. Earlier, we reported the syntheses, structural characterizations and properties of mercury(II) halide compounds in combination with a tetradentate Schiff base, *N,N'*-(bis(pyridin-2-yl)benzylidene)ethane-1,2-diamine¹⁸. In our present endeavour, we have chosen two tridentate Schiff bases, *N,N*-

diethyl-*N'*-(pyridin-2-yl)formylidene)ethane-1,2-diamine (L1) and *N,N*-diethyl-*N'*-(pyridin-2-yl)benzylidene)ethane-1,2-diamine (L2) (Scheme 1) to isolate mercury(II) iodide compounds with different geometries and molecular properties. Successfully, we have isolated two neutral mercury(II) iodide compounds, [Hg(L1)I₂] (1) and [Hg(L2)I₂] (2), from reactions of appropriate building components. The details of syntheses, crystal structures, and thermal and luminescence behaviours of these compounds are described below.

R = H, L1; R = Ph, L2

Scheme 1. (N^a,Nⁱ,N^p) donor set in L1 and L2.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and formulations :

In an effort to isolate iodo bridged neutral polynuclear compounds of the type [Hg₂(L1/L2)I₄]_n, reaction of a

2 : 1 molar ratio of HgI_2 and L1/L2 were performed that resulted in **1**/2 in albeit lower yields. Reactant ratio corresponding to the product stoichiometry (HgI_2 : L1/L2 = 1 : 1) afforded better yields of **1** and **2**. The typical syntheses are summarized in Scheme 2.

Scheme 2. Schematic representation of the reactions.

The new complexes were characterized using microanalytical (C, H and N), spectroscopic, thermal and other physicochemical results. The microanalytical data are in good conformity with the formulations **1** and **2**. The moisture-insensitive complexes are stable over long periods of time in powdery and crystalline states, and are soluble in methanol, ethanol, acetonitrile, dimethylformamide (DMF) and dimethylsulphoxide but are insoluble in water. In DMF solutions they behave as non-electrolytes, as reflected from their low conductivity values ($\sim 5 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$)¹⁹.

Spectroscopic studies :

The Schiff bases, L1 and L2 in the metal bound states exhibit two $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ plus $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ stretching vibrations²⁰ at ~ 1655 – 1635 and ~ 1590 – 1585cm^{-1} ranges. Weak bands in the range 2980 – 2900cm^{-1} are assignable to the aliphatic C–H stretching frequency²⁰. All other characteristic organic ligand vibrations²⁵ are seen in the range 1600 – 600cm^{-1} . In DMF solutions all the complexes **1**

and **2** exhibit absorptions at $\sim 270 \text{nm}$ assignable to ligand based $n-\pi^*/\pi-\pi^*$ transition²¹.

Luminescence properties :

The photoluminescence behaviours of the free Schiff base ligands (L1 and L2) and its compounds (**1** and **2**) are

examined in DMF solutions. The nature of the emission spectra of L1, L2 and **1** and **2** are depicted in Fig. 1. Upon photoexcitation at 270nm , L1 and L2 exhibit a fluorescent emission centered at $\sim 380 \text{nm}$. The com-

Fig. 1. Fluorescence excitation and emission spectra of : L1, L2, **1** and **2** in DMF solutions at room temperature.

pounds **1** and **2**, upon photoexcitations at 270 nm (for **1**) and 271 nm (for **2**) show less intense photoluminescence with the main emission at ~ 380 nm. The luminescence behaviour in **1** and **2** may be attributed to the intraligand $^1(\pi-\pi^*)$ emission²². The decrease in luminous intensity values of the complexes as compared to that of the free ligands (L1 and L2) may presumably be due to the heavy atom effect^{23,24} on ligand upon coordination.

Thermal properties :

To examine thermal stabilities of compounds **1** and **2**, thermogravimetric analyses (TG) were made between 30–700 °C in the static atmosphere of nitrogen. The TG curve (Fig. 2) of **1** shows simultaneous decomposition of one Schiff base (L1) and two terminal iodides (obsd. 78.2%; calcd. 70.1%) in the temperature range 160–434 °C. In

vidual units and perspective views of the packing diagrams for **1** and **2** are shown in Figs. 4 and 5, respectively. Selected bond distances and angles relevant to the coordination spheres of **1** and **2** can be found in Tables 1 and 2, respectively and non-covalent interaction parameters for the complexes are given in Table 3.

Compound **1** has a neutral $[\text{Hg}(\text{L1})\text{I}_2]$ molecular framework (Fig. 4a) whereas the asymmetric unit of **2** contains two neutral $[\text{Hg}(\text{L2})\text{I}_2]$ molecules (Fig. 5a) in which each mercury(II) center adopts a distorted square pyramidal coordination environment [$\tau = 0.16$ in **1** and $\tau = 0.21$ (Hg1) and 0.26 (Hg2) in **2**]²⁵ with HgN_3I_2 chromophore. Three N atoms N^{P} (N1 in **1** and N4 for Hg1 and N7 for Hg2 in **2**), N^{I} (N2 in **1** and N5 for Hg1 and N8 for Hg2 in **2**) and N^{A} (N4 in **1** and N2 for Hg1 and N1 for Hg2 in

Fig. 2. Thermal behaviour of compound **1**.

2, the decomposition commences at 290 °C; TG curve (Fig. 3) shows simultaneous loss of the Schiff base (L2) and two terminal iodides (obsd. 76.1%; calcd. 73.1%) in the temperature range 290–418 °C. The results show that the compounds have reasonable thermal stability in the above temperature range.

Crystal structures :

In order to define the coordination spheres conclusively, single-crystal X-ray diffraction measurements of **1** and **2** were made. ORTEP representations of the indi-

2) of the chelated Schiff bases L1 and L2 in **1** and **2**, respectively along with two terminal I atoms (I2 and I3 in **1**, and I3 and I5 for Hg1 and I4 and I6 for Hg2 in **2**) complete pentacoordination of the bivalent metal. The basal plane consists of three N atoms (N1, N2 and N4 in **1** and N2, N4 and N5 for Hg1 and N1, N7 and N8 for Hg2 in **2**) of L1 and L2 in **1** and **2**, respectively along with one I atom (I3 in **1** and I5 for Hg1 and I6 for Hg2 in **2**), while the apical position is occupied with one I atom (I2 in **1** and I3 for Hg1 and I4 for Hg2 in **2**) of the remaining terminal halide unit. A considerable deviation

Fig. 3. Thermal behaviour of compound 2.

(a)

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4. (a) Molecular structure of **1** with atom labeling scheme and 40% probability ellipsoid for all non-hydrogen atoms. (b) A view of packing diagram of the discrete dimeric $[\text{Hg}(\text{L}1)\text{I}_2]_2$ units in **1** formed through $\pi \cdots \pi$ (green dotted lines) interactions in $[\text{Hg}(\text{L}1)\text{I}_2]$.

(b)

Fig. 5. (a) Asymmetric unit in **2** (ORTEP, 40% thermal ellipsoid). (b) A segment of 1D chain in **2** formed through weak $\text{C}-\text{H} \cdots \text{I}$ hydrogen bonds.

from ideal square pyramidal geometry is seen which is presumably due to the smaller bite angles produced by L1 [$\text{N}2-\text{Hg}1-\text{N}1$ $66.6(2)^\circ$ and $\text{N}2-\text{Hg}1-\text{N}4$ $71.1(2)^\circ$] in **1**

Table 1. Selected bond distances (Å) and angles (°) for **1**

Bond distances :					
Hg1-N1	2.600(6)	Hg1-N4	2.573(6)	Hg1-I3	2.6853(7)
Hg1-N2	2.369(6)	Hg1-I2	2.7365(7)		
Bond angles :					
N2-Hg1-N4	71.1(2)	N4-Hg1-I3	107.17(14)	N1-Hg1-I2	97.18(14)
N2-Hg1-N1	66.6(2)	N1-Hg1-I3	97.64(14)	I3-Hg1-I2	115.21(2)
N4-Hg1-N1	137.6(2)	N2-Hg1-I2	115.57(17)		
N2-Hg1-I3	128.20(17)	N4-Hg1-I2	102.33(14)		

Table 2. Selected bond distances (Å) and angles (°) for **2**

Molecule A :					
Bond distances :					
Hg1-N5	2.398(8)	Hg1-N4	2.567(9)	Hg1-I5	2.7042(10)
Hg1-N2	2.532(8)	Hg1-I3	2.7033(10)		
Bond angles :					
N5-Hg1-N2	71.2(3)	N2-Hg1-I3	100.7(2)	N4-Hg1-I5	91.5(2)
N5-Hg1-N4	65.8(3)	N4-Hg1-I3	105.5(2)	I3-Hg1-I5	122.00(3)
N2-Hg1-N4	135.8(3)	N5-Hg1-I5	123.2(2)		
N5-Hg1-I3	114.2(2)	N2-Hg1-I5	103.97(19)		
Molecule B :					
Bond distances :					
Hg2-N8	2.416(9)	Hg2-N7	2.553(12)	Hg2-I4	2.7010(11)
Hg2-N1	2.516(9)	Hg2-I6	2.6962(10)		
Bond angles :					
N8-Hg2-N1	71.5(3)	N1-Hg2-I6	104.5(2)	N7-Hg2-I4	102.0(3)
N8-Hg2-N7	64.5(3)	N7-Hg2-I6	92.8(3)	I6-Hg2-I4	120.22(3)
N1-Hg2-N7	135.6(3)	N8-Hg2-I4	118.6(2)		
N8-Hg2-I6	120.1(2)	N1-Hg2-I4	103.7(2)		

Table 3

$\pi \cdots \pi$ interaction					
Compound	Ring-Ring	Cg-Cg distance	Dihedral angle (<i>i, j</i>)	Perpendicular distances between baricentres (<i>i, j</i>)	Slippage
1	Cg(3)...Cg(3) ^a	3.817(5)	0	3.550(4)	1.401
Hydrogen bond distances (Å) and angles (°)					
Compound	D-H...A	D-H	H...A	D...A	D-H...A
2	C31-H31B...I6 ^b	0.97	3.04	3.783(12)	134
	C4-H4A...I6 ^c	0.97	3.14	4.108	173
	C28-H28B...I5 ^b	0.97	3.16	3.727	119

Symmetry codes : a = 1-x, 2-y, 1-z; b = 1+x, y, z; c = 1-x, 1/2+y, 1-z; Cg3 : N1-C1-C2-C3-C4-C5.

and L2 [N5-Hg1-N2 71.2(3)° and N5-Hg1-N4 65.8(3)° for Hg1 and N8-Hg2-N1 71.5(3)° and N8-Hg2-N7 64.5(3)° for Hg2] in **2** (Tables 1 and 2). The ethylenic part (N2-C7-C8-N4 of L1 in **1**; N2-C28-C4-N5 for Hg1

and N1-C31-C30-N8 for Hg2 of L2 in **2**) is to some extent puckered. Carbon atom C8 in **1** and C28 for Hg1 and C31 for Hg2 in **2** of the ethylenic part forming the five membered chelate loop at the metal center lie respec-

Table 4. Crystallographic data for [Hg(L1)I₂] (1) and [Hg(L2)I₂] (2)

Crystal parameters	1	2
CCDC No.	852675	852676
Empirical formula	C ₁₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ I ₂ Hg	C ₁₈ H ₂₃ N ₃ I ₂ Hg
Formula weight	659.7	735.8
Temperature (K)	293(2)	293(2)
Wavelength (Å)	0.71073	0.71073
Crystal system	Triclinic	Monoclinic
Space group	P-1	P21
<i>a</i> (Å)	7.9525(11)	8.9838(17)
<i>b</i> (Å)	9.1754(13)	17.437(3)
<i>c</i> (Å)	13.6628(19)	14.199(3)
α (°)	106.088(3)	90.00
β (°)	98.245(3)	93.103(5)
γ (°)	108.339(3)	90.00
Crystal size (mm ³)	0.20 × 0.24 × 0.25	0.07 × 0.19 × 0.21
Volume (Å ³)	879.7(2)	2221.0(7)
Z	2	4
Calculated density (g cm ⁻³)	2.49	2.200
Absorption coefficient (mm ⁻¹)	12.247	9.715
<i>F</i> (000)	596	1352
θ range for data collection (°)	1.60–24.99	1.44–25.67
Limiting indices	-9 < = <i>h</i> < = 9 -10 < = <i>k</i> < = 10 -16 < = <i>l</i> < = 16	-10 < = <i>h</i> < = 10 -21 < = <i>k</i> < = 21 -17 < = <i>l</i> < = 17
<i>T</i> _{min} and <i>T</i> _{max}	0.086 and 0.066	0.50 and 0.15
Reflections collected/unique	8400/3095	22173/8371
Refinement method	Full-matrix least-squares on <i>F</i> ²	Full-matrix least-squares on <i>F</i> ²
Data/restraints/parameters	3095/0/165	8371/1/437
<i>R</i> _{int}	3095	8371
Final <i>R</i> ₁ values (<i>I</i> > 2σ(<i>I</i>))	0.0336	0.0384
Final <i>wR</i> (<i>F</i> ²) values (<i>I</i> > 2σ(<i>I</i>))	0.0702	0.0646
Final <i>R</i> ₁ values (all data)	0.0457	0.0711
Final <i>wR</i> (<i>F</i> ²) values (all data)	0.0758	0.0758
Goodness of fit on <i>F</i> ²	1.034	0.878
Largest peak and hole (eÅ ⁻³)	0.541 and -1.168	0.438 and -0.547
Weighting scheme : $R_1 = \frac{\sum F_o - F_c }{\sum F_o }$, $wR = \frac{[\sum w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2 / \sum w(F_o^2)^2]}{1/2}$, Calcd. $w = 1/[\sigma^2(F_o^2) + (0.0329P)^2 + 0.0000P]$ (1) and Calcd. $w = 1/[\sigma^2(F_o^2) + (0.0000P)^2 + 0.0000P]$ (2); where $P = (F_o^2 + 2F_c^2)/3$.		

tively 0.616 Å and 0.679 Å for Hg1 and 0.683 Å for Hg2 above the plane (N2, C7, N4 and Hg1 in 1 and N2, C4, N5 and Hg1, N1, C30, N8 and Hg2 in 2) in the direction of apical halide. In 1, Hg1 atom deviates 0.791 Å from the mean plane (N1, N2, N4 and I3) towards the apical I2 whereas the deviation of Hg1/Hg2 in 2 from the mean plane (N2, N4, N5, I5 for Hg1 and N1, N7, N8, I6 for Hg2) towards the apical I3/I4 is 0.930/0.941 Å.

In the crystal packing, two mononuclear units of 1 are associated by weak $\pi \cdots \pi$ interactions (Table 3) involving pyridine rings [Cg3 : N1-C1-C2-C3-C4-C5] of L1 resulting in a discrete dimer with Hg1...Hg1 separation 8.978 Å. The dimeric entities are oriented (Fig. 4b) in such a fashion that prevents further $\pi \cdots \pi$ interaction among them. In 2, the monomeric units are packed through C-H...I interactions (Table 3) into a 1D chain along a-axis (Fig.

5b). The Hg1...Hg1/Hg2...Hg2 and Hg1...Hg2 separations are 8.984 and 8.453 Å, respectively.

Conclusion :

In conclusion, two neutral mercury(II) iodide complexes in combination with two tridentate Schiff bases (L1 and L2) are isolated and X-ray crystallographically characterized. These compounds afford different crystalline architectures through multiple weak non-covalent forces. The work on such compounds illustrates a potentially versatile approach towards isolation of uncharged metal-organic frameworks.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

High purity pyridine-2-carboxaldehyde (Lancaster, UK), 2-benzoylpyridine (Lancaster, UK), *N,N*-diethylethane-1,2-diamine (SRL, India) and mercury(II) iodide (E. Merck, India) were purchased from respective concerns and used as received. The Schiff bases, (*N,N*-diethyl-*N'*-(pyridin-2-yl)formylidene)ethane-1,2-diamine (L1) and (*N,N*-diethyl-*N'*-(pyridin-2-yl)benzylidene)ethane-1,2-diamine (L2) were prepared following the reported methods described elsewhere²⁶. All other chemicals and solvents used were AR grade. The synthetic reactions and work-up were done in open air.

Elemental analyses (carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen) were performed on a Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNS/O elemental analyzer. IR spectra (KBr discs, 4000–400 cm⁻¹) were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer FTIR model RX1 spectrometer. Molar conductances were measured using a Systronics conductivity meter where the cell constant was calibrated with 0.01(*M*) KCl solution, and DMF was used as solvent. Thermal behaviour was examined with a Perkin-Elmer Diamond TG/DT analyzer heated from 30–700 °C under nitrogen. Ground state absorption and steady-state fluorescence measurements (in DMF) were made with a Shimadzu model UV-2450 UV-Vis spectrophotometer and a Hitachi model F-4010 spectrofluorimeter, respectively.

Preparation of the complex :

[Hg(L1)I₂] (1) : L1 (0.102 g, 0.5 mmol) in methanol (20 ml) was added slowly to HgI₂ (0.227 g, 0.5 mmol) solution dissolved in acetonitrile (20 ml) and reaction mixture was stirred continuously for 15 min. The result-

ing orange-yellow solution was filtered and left undisturbed in an open air for slow evaporation. After a few days, crystals of **1** were isolated by filtration, washed with dehydrated alcohol and dried *in vacuo* over silica gel. Yield : 0.474 g (72%) (Found : C, 21.7; H, 2.8; N, 6.2. Calcd. for C₁₂H₁₉N₃I₂Hg (1) : C, 21.8; H, 2.9; N, 6.4%); IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : ν(C-H) 2976, 2932; ν(C=N) + ν(C=C) 1655, 1587; UV-Vis (DMF, λ_{max}/nm) : 276; Λ_M (DMF, Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) : 6.

[Hg(L2)I₂] (2) : For preparation and isolation of **2** in pure crystalline state, similar reaction condition and reaction stoichiometry as used in **1** were followed except that L2 (0.140 g, 0.5 mmol) instead of L1 was used. The light yellow solution was processed as in **1**. Yield : 0.522 g (71%) (Found : C, 29.2; H, 3.2; N, 5.6. Calcd. for C₁₈H₂₃N₃I₂Hg (2) : C, 29.4; H, 3.2; N, 5.7%); IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : ν(C-H) 2979, 2922, 2858; ν(C=N) + ν(C=C) 1638, 1586; UV-Vis (DMF, λ_{max}/nm) : 274; Λ_M (DMF, Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) : 5.

X-Ray crystallographic analysis :

Single crystals of **1** and **2** suitable for X-ray analyses were selected from those obtained by slow evaporation of methanol-acetonitrile solution mixtures at 298 K. Diffraction data were collected on a Bruker SMART APEX-II CCD area-detector diffractometer at 293 K using graphite monochromated Mo-Kα radiation (λ = 0.71073 Å). For unit cell determination, the single crystal was exposed with X-ray for 10 s in three frames. The detector frames were integrated by use of the program SAINT²⁷ and absorption corrections were performed with SADABS²⁸. The structures were solved by direct methods, using the SHELXTL²⁹ program. All atomic displacement parameters for non-hydrogen atoms have been refined with anisotropic term. For all structures, the hydrogen atoms were fixed geometrically and refined using a riding model. All calculations were carried out using SHELXTL²⁹, PLATON³⁰ and ORTEP-3³¹ programs. Further details are given in Table 1.

Supplementary data :

Crystallographic data (excluding structure factors) for **1** and **2** have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre No. CCDC 852675 for **1** and 852676 for **2**. Copies of this information can be obtained, free of charge from The Director, CCDC, 12 Union Road,

Cambridge, CB2 1EZ, UK (Fax : 44-1223-336033; E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk or http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk).

Acknowledgement

Financial support from DST and CSIR, New Delhi, India is gratefully acknowledged. The authors also acknowledge the use of DST-funded National Single Crystal X-ray Diffraction Facility at the Department of Inorganic Chemistry, IACS, Kolkata, India for crystallographic studies. KB, SS and SC are grateful to CSIR, New Delhi, India for fellowships.

References

1. P. Comba, T. W. Hambley and B. Martin, "Molecular Modeling of Inorganic Compounds", 3rd ed., Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, 2009.
2. J. N. Lalena and D. A. Cleary, "Principles of Inorganic Materials Design", 2nd ed., John Wiley & Sons Inc., Hoboken, New Jersey, 2010.
3. A. Morsali and M. Y. Masoomi, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2009, **253**, 1882; M. Nolte, I. Pantenburg and G. Meyer, *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 2005, **631**, 2923.
4. J.-Y. Cheng, Y.-B. Dong, R.-Q. Huang and M. D. Smith, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2005, **358**, 891; M. S. Bharara, S. Parkin and D. A. Atwood, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2006, **45**, 2112.
5. G. Mahmoudi, A. Morsali, A. D. Hunter and M. Zeller, *CrystEngComm.*, 2007, **9**, 274.
6. G. Mahmoudi and A. Morsali, *Cryst. Growth Des.*, 2008, **8**, 391.
7. K. Huber, "Wisconsin Mercury Source Book", Section 3, Madison, Wisconsin, 1997, 67; S.-K. Ko, Y.-K. Yang, J. Tac and I. Shin, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **128**, 14150.
8. A. Tamayo, B. Pedras, C. Lodeiro, L. Escriche, J. Casabo, J. L. Capelo, B. Covelo, R. Kivekas and R. Sillanpaa, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2007, **46**, 7818; S. Park, S. Y. Lee and S. S. Lee, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2010, **49**, 1238.
9. J. J. Perry, J. A. Perman and M. J. Zaworotko, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2009, **38**, 1400.
10. B. Cornils, W. A. Herrmann and R. Schlogl (eds.), "Catalysis from A to Z : A Concise Encyclopedia", John Wiley & Sons, New York, 2000; J. R. Farraro and J. M. Williams, "Introduction to Synthetic Electrical Conductors", Academic Press, New York, 1987.
11. J. W. Grate, *Chem. Rev.*, 2000, **100**, 2627; V. Balzani, A. Credi and M. Venturi, "Molecular Devices and Machines", Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, 2003.
12. V. Alexander, *Chem. Rev.*, 1995, **95**, 273; P. A. Vigato, S. Tamburini and L. Bertolo, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2007, **251**, 1311.
13. U. Englert, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2010, **254**, 537.
14. X.-F. Wang, Y. Lv, T.-A. Okamura, H. Kawaguchi, G. Wu, W.-Y. Sun and N. Ueyama, *Cryst. Growth Des.*, 2007, **7**, 1125; D.-Z. Wang, C.-S. Liu, J.-R. Li, L. Li, Y.-F. Zeng and X.-H. Bu, *CrystEngComm.*, 2007, **9**, 289.
15. P. J. Steel, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 2005, **38**, 243.
16. G. R. Desiraju and T. Steiner, "The Weak Hydrogen Bond in Structural Chemistry and Biology", OUP, Oxford, 1999.
17. T. Kawase and H. Kurata, *Chem. Rev.*, 2006, **106**, 5250.
18. S. Satapathi, S. Chattopadhyay, S. Roy, K. Bhar. P. Mitra and B. K. Ghosh, *J. Mol. Struct.*, article in press, doi: 10.1016/j.molstruc.2012.03.027.
19. W. J. Geary, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
20. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Part B. 5th ed., John Wiley & Sons, New Jersey, 2009.
21. A. B. P. Lever, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", 2nd ed., Elsevier, New York, 1984; J. Garcia Sole, L. E. Bausa and D. Jaque, "An Introduction to the Optical Spectroscopy", John Wiley & Sons, New York, 2005.
22. Q.-G. Zhai, X.-Y. Wu, S.-M. Chen, C.-Z. Lu and W.-B. Yang, *Cryst. Growth Des.*, 2006, **6**, 2126; Y. Liu, P.-F. Yan, Y.-H. Yu, G.-F. Hou, J.-S. Gao and J. Y. Lu, *Cryst. Growth Des.*, 2010, **10**, 1559.
23. J. R. Lakowicz, "Principles of Fluorescence Spectroscopy", 3rd ed., Springer, USA, 2006.
24. K. J. Wei, Y. S. Xie, J. Ni, M. Zhang and Q. L. Liu, *Cryst. Growth Des.*, 2006, **6**, 1341; F. Zeng, J. Ni, Q. Wang, Y. Ding, S. Weng Ng, W. Zhu and Y. Xie, *Cryst. Growth Des.*, 2010, **10**, 1611.
25. A. W. Addison, T. N. Rao, J. Reedijk, J. V. Rijn and G. C. Verschoor, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1984, 1349.
26. S. H. Rahaman, H. Chowdhury, D. Bose, R. Ghosh, C.-H. Hung and B. K. Ghosh, *Polyhedron*, 2005, **24**, 1755.
27. SAINT Plus, v.6.01, Bruker Analytical X-Ray, Madison, WI, 1999.
28. SADABS v.2.01, Bruker/Siemens Area Detector Absorption Correction Program, Bruker AXS, Madison, Wisconsin, USA, 1998.
29. G. M. Sheldrick, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 2008, **A64**, 112.
30. A. L. Spek, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 2009, **D65**, 148.
31. L. J. Farrugia, ORTEP-3, *J. Appl. Crystallogr.*, 1997, **30**, 565.